

**JUST
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4 ALL**

T3.2 NORTH-EAST REGION (BG) REGIONAL REPORT

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Authors: Konstantin Uzunov, Dr. Mariya Trifonova

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Description	Overview of historical evolution of the wind energy industry encompassing regional and temporal demarcation, a summary of phases and critical instances of change, and a comprehensive list of wind energy projects/initiatives. The primary focus is on the case study of Severoiztochen (North-East Region), Bulgaria, with the intent to later delve deeper into two selected projects for more extensive research.

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DISCLAIMER AND FORWARD

This case study about wind energy developments in the North-East region, Bulgaria has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All (JW4A) project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (over 50), 5 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and historical policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and across the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

Bulgaria, situated in Southeastern Europe, boasts a diverse energy landscape driven by a combination of fossil fuels and renewable energy sources. As a significant electricity producer and exporter in the region, Bulgaria plays a crucial role in the Balkans' energy balance. However, the country's energy market is dominated by state-owned players with major market share in the energy industry. The state's predominant role as an energy asset owner significantly impacts the governance of the key energy sector in Bulgaria and hinders the progress of transitioning towards low-carbon energy sources. To ensure a greener future, Bulgaria must prioritize the adoption of green technologies, not only for environmental protection but also to enhance the competitiveness of its SMEs in both national and international markets.¹ Moreover, the favorable geographical features of Bulgarian regions present ample opportunities for harnessing renewable energy resources.

Despite the promising potential for wind energy in coastal regions, such as the North-East region, it remains underutilized due to the unfriendly national policy towards the wind energy sector. Addressing these policy challenges it is essential to unlock the full potential of wind energy and contribute significantly to Bulgaria's sustainable energy objectives. Therefore when discussing obstacles for the wind energy deployment, this case study addresses key developments and policies on national level in addition to regional specifics.

1.1.1. ENERGY SYSTEM

The country's power sector is well-established and interconnected with neighboring nations. Historically, conventional energy sources such as coal, nuclear, and natural gas have dominated the national energy mix and hydropower was the only one source of renewable energy before early 2000s, when EU legislation promoting renewable energy has started to be transposed into the national legal framework.

Lignite coal, produced domestically, contributes to 37% of the country's power generation (as of 2021). In alignment with the objectives of the European Green Deal, the government has committed to phasing out coal (4.5 GW power capacity at the moment) and reducing its share in the energy mix. However, a concrete coal phase-out date is yet to be announced, and the transition planning remains somewhat uncertain for the future.

The Kozloduy Nuclear Power Plant plays a crucial and strategic role in Bulgaria's energy supply, as it currently accounts for 35% of the country's electricity generation. To address future energy demands and strengthen their nuclear capabilities, Bulgaria has been engaged in discussions about new nuclear reactor projects. Notably, in the summer of 2023, Westinghouse and Bulgaria's Kozloduy NPP-Newbuild have joined forces and formed a joint working group. Their primary objective is to assess the feasibility of constructing an AP1000 reactor on the existing Kozloduy site.

One of the factors contributing to the positive outlook on nuclear power in Bulgaria is the historically high social acceptability towards this technology. Nuclear energy has been viewed positively due to

¹ <https://csd.bg/publications/publication/promoting-constructive-capital-in-bulgaria/>

its association with modernity and its reputation for successfully implementing high-tech projects in the energy sector. At present, no concrete decisions have been made regarding the new reactor projects. However, a considerable portion of policymakers in Bulgaria are enthusiastic about pursuing the construction of two new reactors, which could potentially add 2 GW of nuclear capacity to the Kozloduy Nuclear Power Plant. Ultimately, any decision made will have a substantial impact on Bulgaria's energy landscape.

The consumption of natural gas has significantly declined in recent times due to energy crises and disturbances in supplies from Russia. However, natural gas continues to be an important energy source, particularly for heating and industrial applications. Bulgaria has managed to diversify its supply sources within a few months to mitigate the impact of these disruptions.

Figure 1. Gross electricity generation per source in Bulgaria

Source: Data of the Electricity Transmission System Operator, www.eso.bg

Bulgaria has made considerable progress in developing renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, biomass, and hydroelectric power. These sources play a vital role in the country's efforts to decarbonize its energy sector. Hydropower has historically played an important role in the energy mix. However, the large, pumped storage HPPs Chaira is currently out of operation due to unsuccessful repair projects and inconsistencies in identifying the reasons for the damage. There are expectations for partial commissioning again in 2025. During periods of rising electricity prices and shortages, hydropower plants would ease pressure on the system and offer cheaper electricity during peak consumption times. HPP Chaira is the largest pumped-storage plant in Southeastern Europe, with a total electricity generation capacity of 864 MW (almost equivalent to one nuclear reactor). If the "Yadenitsa" reservoir project, costing around 300 million euros, is completed, "Chaira" could operate much more and become the largest energy battery in the region, providing Bulgaria with a significant competitive advantage in the energy transformation. Despite a 30% reduction in power generation

from state-owned hydroelectric power plants in 2022, water levels are approximately 8.5% lower than the average for the previous years this season. This necessitates more cautious management of hydroelectric power plants, given their role in balancing Bulgaria's electricity grid.

The figure below illustrates the installed capacity and power generation from other renewable energy sources. Solar power has experienced significant growth in recent years as many industrial and commercial companies have installed PV modules on their roofs to reduce electricity costs and access low-carbon energy. On the other hand, the situation with wind power is different. Although many projects are under development, the last wind power station was connected to the system in 2014, and the share of wind in the installed renewable energy capacity remains stable. The challenges lie in a cumbersome administrative procedure, non-transparent rules for grid connection and cost allocation, the concentration of wind resources in the Northeastern part of Bulgaria, some of which fall within nature-protected areas, and social unacceptability in certain municipalities due to targeted anti-renewable energy campaigns.

Figure 2: New additions and generated power by renewable energy source based on recent data.

Source: Bulgarian Sustainable Energy Agency (end of 2023).

The initial boom in renewables (2008-2013) was largely driven by feed-in-tariffs, but currently, only small rooftop PV installations qualify for financial support from the state. Larger projects installed after 2018 operate entirely market-based.

Under the National Recovery and Resilience Facility, a crucial component of the NextGeneration EU financial package, there are plans to incentivize decentralized generation and consumption of renewable energy, as well as the introduction of alternative business models. The proposed measures include establishing one-stop shops for operators of renewable power plants, streamlining administrative procedures, and evaluating existing mechanisms in other countries for financing energy efficiency. The plan foresees a greater utilization of renewable energy in households (the Green Bulgaria Pillar) and in various business sectors (the Innovative Bulgaria Pillar) through the introduction of renewable energy auctions. However, the document does not provide specific rules for energy communities, and the proposed auction design appears to favor larger plants. It should be noted that the auction is significantly delayed, and as the project needs to be finalized by 2026 according to the framework of the financial scheme, it is not expected that the wind projects will be able to qualify for investment aid.

A recent study conducted by the Austrian Institute of Technology in collaboration with the local public policy institute CSD estimates that Northeastern Bulgaria, encompassing the districts of Varna, Dobrich, Shumen, and Razgrad, holds the potential for at least 10 GW of installed onshore wind capacity. This region boasts high average wind speeds, minimal land use barriers, and favorable environmental conditions.

Furthermore, nearly a third of the Bulgarian coastline is identified as suitable for offshore wind energy development, with a potential total installed capacity of nearly 176 GW. While estimations regarding the technical potential of offshore wind, as provided by various sources such as the World Bank, JRC, and CSD, vary significantly, it is evident that Bulgaria possesses significant offshore wind power potential, which remains largely untapped. This potential has garnered attention from policymakers, particularly in the aftermath of the Russian invasion in Ukraine.

In 2022 Bulgaria has initiated the necessary strategic and legal groundwork, although specific deployment targets and legal procedures are still lacking. Last year, a comprehensive offshore renewable energy law was introduced in the National Parliament, proposing two approaches for site development, tenders for promising areas and integration of offshore wind deployment areas into the national Marine Spatial Plan (MSP). In early 2024, the law passed its first reading in Parliament. However, prior to the second reading, it encountered significant opposition from the tourism sector, fisheries, and the nuclear lobby in Bulgaria, particularly as the country was anticipating the construction of two new reactors alongside the projected launch of its first offshore wind energy projects. In the week leading up to the second reading, the law became a bargaining chip between the political parties within the coalition government, which were negotiating a shift in the government. Therefore, the future of this legal act remains uncertain.

The first demonstration project, supported by the European Commission, is expected to install the first wind turbine based on floating concept in the Bulgarian section of the Black Sea. While the technical potential for offshore wind energy in the Bulgarian section is estimated at 116 GW, with a fifth achievable using mature bottom-fixed technology, the anticipated new additions until 2040 are modest, reaching only 3-4 GW. Collaborative efforts with Romania are recognized to foster a common market for interested investors, transform shared port infrastructure, secure funding for preliminary investigations and cross-border projects, and enhance offshore and onshore grid infrastructure.

1.1.2. MAIN STAKEHOLDERS AT NATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL

In Bulgaria, wind energy planning and sustainable deployment involve several key stakeholders at both the national and regional levels. These stakeholders play crucial roles in shaping policies, regulations, and decision-making processes related to wind energy development.

The **Ministry of Energy** is a state institution responsible for formulating and implementing the energy policy of Bulgaria. It plays a central role in the country's energy sector, including wind energy. The Ministry of Energy is in charge of setting overall renewable energy targets, facilitating wind energy projects, providing incentives or subsidies for wind energy development, and overseeing the operations of state-owned energy companies (no state-owned company owns or operates wind energy generation assets). **Ministry of Environment and Water** is responsible for environmental protection, including matters related to renewable energy projects. In the context of wind energy, this ministry assesses the environmental impact of wind farms, ensures compliance with environmental regulations and standards, and issues permits or approvals for wind energy projects based on their

environmental impact assessments. **The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works** is involved in spatial planning and infrastructure development across different regions in Bulgaria. In relation to offshore wind energy projects, three other ministries are important stakeholders, particularly in terms of planning of deployment areas and co-existence, **Ministry of Transport, Ministry of Defence and Ministry of Tourism**.

The **Energy and Water Regulatory Commission** determines annually preferential prices for the purchase of electricity from renewable sources. The authority approves annually until June 30 the amount of electric power from renewable energy sources that could be connected to transmission and distribution electrical networks structured by connection areas and voltage levels and publishes the data on its webpage. The Commission issues also permits for operation and energy generation licenses. Guarantees of energy origin are issued by the **Agency for Sustainable Energy Development (AUER)**. One unit covers the power generation of 1 MWh, valid for 12 months. The Agency shall establish and maintain an electronic register of guarantees of origin, data from which he publishes on his website. This is the only one register of RE plant operator.

At the regional level, local **municipality governments and regional authorities** play an essential role in wind energy planning and deployment. They are responsible for issuing permits for wind energy projects within their jurisdictions, taking into account local regulations, land-use plans, and community interests. Local energy agencies, as well as the **Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies** as an umbrella association, play a significant role in promoting and supporting renewable energy projects, including wind energy. They provide expertise, technical support, and information dissemination to various stakeholders involved in the sector.

Private stakeholders, project developers and gas exploitation companies interested in wind energy projects are significant stakeholders. For the North-East region the most relevant are CWP, WPD, AES, Longman Holding, Petrocelktik and Total Energies among others. Many of the project developers with existing onshore wind parks are represented in the **Bulgarian Wind Energy Association (BGWEA)** as well as **Association for Energy Production, Storage and Trade (APSTE)**.

The development of wind energy clusters can bring significant opportunities for **ports** in Bulgaria. Ports can become crucial logistical hubs for the import and export of wind turbine components and equipment. As wind farms are developed offshore, ports can also serve as bases for installation vessels and maintenance operations, creating new jobs and economic activity in port regions. **Industrial companies from the cement and chemicals sectors** based in the Nord-Eastern region (Devnya) can benefit from large-scale renewable energy generation in the region and should be kept involved. They may choose to invest in on-site wind farms to meet their energy needs sustainably, reducing their reliance on conventional energy sources and enhancing their environmental credentials. Wind energy can also play a pivotal role in the production of green hydrogen through electrolysis. As wind power generates electricity, excess power can be used to produce hydrogen, which can be used as a clean fuel for various applications, such as transportation or industrial processes. This creates synergies between wind energy and **hydrogen facilities operators**, promoting a sustainable energy ecosystem. The growth of wind energy in Bulgaria, particularly offshore wind, can create opportunities for **ship manufacturers** and the existing Marine Cluster, based in Varna.

Greenpeace, WWF, Zeleni Zakoni, Bulgarian Bird Protection Society are environmental organizations which play a crucial role in monitoring wind energy projects' environmental impact and advocating for responsible and sustainable development. They can engage in dialogue with stakeholders to ensure that wind farms are designed and operated with minimal adverse effects on local ecosystems and wildlife. The **Institute for Oceanology and the Institute of Ornithology**, both affiliated with the

Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, are scientific research institutions instrumental in conducting studies and collecting data on the potential ecological effects of offshore wind farms on marine life and bird populations. Their research can inform decision-making and help design wind energy projects that protect biodiversity and natural habitats. In the summer of 2023, the establishment of the **Black Sea Renewable Energy Coalition** has been announced, which serves as an informal network of collaborators and facilitates knowledge exchange and collaboration among infrastructural operators, project developers and environmental stakeholders involved in marine renewable energy projects in the area. It can also provide a platform for addressing common challenges and opportunities related to renewable energy development at sea.

The national TSO (**ESO EAD**) plays a vital role in integrating wind energy into the national grid seamlessly. Collaborating with environmental organizations can help ensure that grid integration is carried out in a manner that minimizes potential impacts on wildlife and sensitive ecological areas.

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

The Bulgarian regional case study focuses on the opportunities for wind energy development in the **North-East planning region of Bulgaria (Severoiztochen)** according to the European NUTS 2 classification. The region is estimated to have a **high wind potential**, both on- and offshore with a large part still unrealised potential. The reasons for this will be explained in detail in the course of the study. However, the majority of Bulgaria's onshore wind energy capacity is concentrated in this particular region, accounting for a significant 80% of the country's total 700 MW generation capacity. This figure translates to 108 out of 160 installations, as reported by Trifonova (2021), based on data from the Bulgarian Sustainable Energy Agency. Notably, the case study region also boasts the largest marine areas with optimal wind energy resources, while also demonstrating minimal conflicts with other economic activities and environmental conservation efforts. These factors make it an ideal location for further exploration and development of wind energy projects, especially considering its proximity to the coastal areas.

The region presents an intriguing opportunity for in-depth exploration for a couple of compelling reasons. Firstly, it serves as an appropriate **test ground for exploring and experimenting with various participatory practices** in the context of wind energy development. Interestingly, the perception of wind energy among different social groups varies significantly across districts and municipalities within the region's boundaries. While some areas exhibit positive attitudes towards wind energy, others still bear the influence of negative campaigns from the past.

The reasons behind these varying perceptions are complex and often subjective, making it a challenge to analyze and engage these diverse social formations in constructive dialogue. Nonetheless, the region's strength lies in **the presence of several smaller municipalities** (such as Kavarna, Dobrich, Balchik) that actively embrace wind energy initiatives and possess the capacity to manage them effectively.

Despite the existence of myths and protest groups, as described further in the text, notable progress has been achieved in showcasing positive examples and highlighting the **beneficial impacts of wind energy on the local economy and natural environment within the region**. It underscores the potential for further advancements and serves as inspiration for encouraging wider acceptance and cooperation in embracing sustainable energy solutions.

The **region also borders Romania**, which has achieved great progress in the use of wind energy in recent years. The results are particularly impressive in terms of their offshore wind governance and

technology transfer. The Bulgarian North-East region's proximity to Romania is on the one hand a good opportunity for exchange of experience and on the other a chance for managing authorities and private investors from both countries to develop joint projects. The potential to create **an energy island in the Black Sea**, built jointly by Bulgaria and Romania would seriously support achieving both states' renewable energy targets. In addition, such large-scale projects would develop systemic capacity to connect with the other Black Sea countries and thus leverage the investments. Various options for such joint projects are currently under discussion, the expectations are that with the development of regulations in Bulgaria a rapid deployment of offshore wind energy installations will be unleashed along with the transfer of new technologies such as floating and airborne turbines.

1.2.1 REGIONAL DEMARCATION

The North-East region is one of the six NUTS 2 planning regions in Bulgaria that includes four provinces – Varna, Dobrich, Turgovishte and Shumen. The largest cities are Varna (341 737 - city proper), Dobrich (79 269), Shumen (85 410), Silistra (43 265). The GDP of the region is EUR 7 093 million against EUR 70 986 million for the country (National Statistical Institute, 2021). Varna is the largest maritime city in Bulgaria called the seaside capital. The port of Varna is the largest port in Bulgaria and the third largest on the Black Sea. On the Danube river, important ports are Silistra – fourth largest on the river, and Tutrakan. The transformation of the two largest Bulgarian ports (Varna and Burgas in the South-East region) to decarbonization hubs would substantially support the offshore wind industry. Open questions are to what extent, in what governance arrangements and with what intensity.

In the context of JustWind4All project, there is no need to limit the regional demarcation of the region within its geographical borders, but on the contrary – rather to build on what has been done so far and expand it throughout the country, involving more stakeholders in order to develop sustainable systematic links and partnerships. This way we will maximize on the impacts, enhancing knowledge and technology transfer. It is important to remain as much as possible open for collaborations and look up for synergies between the different wind projects, initiatives, participation practices and smoothen the communication between the different units, both at institutional, business and academic level. This approach is conditioned by the national specifics of the country in which a small number of sectoral and institutional players operate.

Although, the focus was placed on smaller municipalities that are already actively developing wind projects or have been identified as territories with high potential for such energy developments and/or have already attracted investors' interest. Particular wind turbine sites and initiatives, including stakeholders/investors with declared interests to develop both offshore and onshore wind farms are objects of the study.

Figure 3. Map of the North-East region (NUTS2), Bulgaria

Figure 2. Map of offshore areas in the North-East region

1.2.2 TEMPORAL DEMARCATION

As the key phases and relevant instances of change have been sporadic for the last 20 years the North-East region **case study focuses on the key developments in the sector after 2018 to 2023** (5 years focus period). Although the very first R&D phase dates back to the early 1980s, the pre-period covered in the study is from 2007 to 2018. In 2007 Bulgaria joined the EU and accepted key mandatory regulations and obligations to be applied for the development of renewable energy production which became a prerequisite for dynamic development in the sector. Emblematic phases took place in the pre-period such as: the 1st commercial projects wave (2007-2010); “boom” in the sector development (2010-2012), followed by “freezing” and decline in investor’s interest until 2018.

The North-East region belongs to the group of regions with a 'shorter' history of wind energy development, i.e. less than approximately 20 years. But this framing is conditional, as the very first pilot installations and R&D developments have been exploited significantly earlier.

We can conclude the time period of 2018 to 2023 as a relevant temporal demarcation for the given case study (focus period).

1.3 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

The aim of this case study is to outline the key dimensions of the governance of wind energy development in the Nord-Eastern region of Bulgaria. As this region houses a significant concentration of the country's wind energy industry, the report also encompasses national policies, policy priorities, and key events that have shaped institutional and structural changes. Given that the wind energy industry in Bulgaria is relatively young, with developments starting around 2005, the case study spans an observation period of the last 20 years. The study seeks to develop an understanding of the regional challenges and opportunities related to wind energy governance. Additionally, the study aims to outline future perspectives, considering governance deficits and regional strengths that hold relevance for the emerging sector of offshore wind energy. Ultimately, the goal is to generate key recommendations that foster energy citizenship and contribute to the effectiveness and fairness of wind energy governance in the Nord-Eastern region. By addressing governance issues and leveraging regional strengths, this study endeavors to promote a sustainable and inclusive wind energy sector that aligns with Bulgaria's broader energy goals.

To set the context, the report begins with an introduction providing an overview of the country's energy system and relevant developments. It highlights the growing importance of wind energy as part of Bulgaria's renewable energy portfolio. The regional context is then outlined, with a focus on the Nord-Eastern region's unique features that make it attractive for wind energy development. The temporal demarcation is specified, covering the past 5-10 years, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the region's wind energy governance landscape.

In the methodological section, the report details the data collection and analysis approach. It highlights the use of interviews, document reviews, participant observation, and focus groups to gather information from various stakeholders. Empirical reflections discuss the challenges encountered during data collection and their implications for the study's outcomes.

The report then delves into the wind energy governance in the Nord-Eastern region across different phases. It starts with a pre-period overview to provide historical context. Subsequent sections focus on specific timeframes, analyzing critical instances of change that influenced wind energy development. This multi-phased approach allows for a thorough understanding of wind energy governance evolution over the study period.

In the analysis and discussion section, the report examines the data collected and engages in a comprehensive discussion of findings. It addresses regional challenges and opportunities in wind energy governance, shedding light on factors influencing decision-making processes.

Finally, the report synthesizes key insights and presents recommendations to foster energy citizenship and improve wind energy governance in the Nord-Eastern region. These recommendations aim to promote sustainable and inclusive development by considering the interests of various stakeholders involved in the wind energy sector.

Throughout the study, a range of stakeholders, including environmental organizations, research institutions, and the national Transmission System Operator (TSO), are considered. The report acknowledges the crucial role these entities play in shaping wind energy governance and emphasizes the need for collaboration and stakeholder engagement to ensure just and effective development in the region.

2 KEY INSIGHTS

Overview of key insights about **just and effective wind energy governance** from the case study in bullet points (these could be focused on specific actors, something we can discuss as we draw closer towards actually formulating those)

2.1.1 INSTANCES OF PARTICIPATION

- The instances of participation (participatory practices) that were chosen for further exploitation are characterized by their scale and potential to impact the development of the wind sector in the country. Although, the two are fundamentally different from each other.
- **The first** is a regional one but contains everything necessary for good practice that can be applied internationally. **It is a unique configuration of a Integrated Bird Protection System (Early Warning System)**, which involves twelve Bulgarian companies that own and operate wind energy farms located near the town of Kavarna (North-East region). The St. Nicholas wind farm was a leading party in establishing the Integrated Early Warning System for the Protection of Birds.
- **Its aim is to ensure the most effective protection of birds with joint efforts, which is an example of successful cooperation between many participants applied on a large territory.**
- The Early Warning System complies with European requirements for the protection of wild birds and allows to manage and minimize the risk of bird collision with the rotating parts of wind turbines, by shutting down single or groups of turbines, or entire wind farms, as well as monitoring during risk periods for species of conservation importance. Expert ornithologists work in the field to carry out data analysis and monitoring on a daily basis.
- This joint initiative of the operators is not only a successful example of cooperation in a specific important activity for the sector, but also a mechanism for dialogue with certain social groups, incl. protest groups that have concerns about the conservation of certain bird and animal species.
- **The second one** covers the key legislative processes, especially participation in the planning process of different stakeholder groups related to the proposal of a Law for the energy from renewable sources in the sea spaces. It entered the Parliament in 2022, also covering the offshore energy issues, but because of the political crisis in the country it was delayed and is not a fact yet.
- The process is very both intense and curious as the law has been postponed several times and the law texts have undergone adjustments for various political, economic and social reasons serving different purposes.
- However, the Law is quite important as special attention is given to the country's marine spaces and offshore wind utilization.
- In order to unlock the potential in that direction, which according to the latest data of the Center for the Study of Democracy is huge, a consistent and transparent system regulation is needed to set up the right long-term priorities and manage the mechanisms for achieving

them. It is also extremely important to consider the various opportunities and stakeholder groups, including energy cooperatives. In Bulgaria, there is no working legal framework for energy communities, whose role is growing and opportunities are growing in countries with a high RES share.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The case study undertaken for wind energy project development in the North-East region involved a comprehensive data collection and analysis process. To gain valuable insights, five individuals actively involved in wind energy projects were interviewed between May and August 2023. A purposive sampling strategy ensured representation from diverse sectors, including industry, academia, and environmental organizations. The **principle of diversity** has been applied which is illustrated by the table with the profiles of the interviewees published below. The most important criterion for choosing the respondents have been their long experience in/with the wind industry and good knowledge of all historical events from 2005 until now. The identification of the suitable participants was based on personal contacts and recommendations.

Table 1. Profile of the interviewees

	Gender	Sectoral representation	Professional experience in the professional field	Attitude towards wind energy industry in region
Interviewee 1	Female	Industrial association	14 years	Positive
Interviewee 2	Male	Project Developer	14 years	Positive
Interviewee 3	Female	Project Developer	15 years	Positive
Interviewee 4	Male	Academia/ Environment	30 years in academia and directly working with the wind industry since 2009 (14 years)	Subjective
Interviewee 5	Male	Academia/ Environment	not directly contributing to the wind industry, but potential impact on unlocking offshore wind industry	Not defined, rather subjective

The semi-structured interviews covered various aspects of wind energy development in Bulgaria, exploring events, actors contributing to institutional and structural changes, as well as identified participatory practices and governance strengths and deficits. Additionally, attitudes towards the emerging offshore wind energy industry were assessed. The interview responses underwent

systematic coding, with open coding techniques revealing themes and unique viewpoints. To enhance data credibility, a critical analysis was conducted to validate the findings.

Furthermore, the study aimed to understand historical factors to implement more effective and just mechanisms for managing wind power arrangements in the future. This objective, along with the regional Wind Lab activities planned during the project, formed an essential part of the research.

To establish a historical context and enrich the interview data, aspects of the evolution of the RES sector in Bulgaria from the early 2020s were integrated based on the work of M. Trifonova from her 2021 PhD thesis. A systematic literature review analyzed 11 selected academic papers out of 86 initially screened, covering the period between 2009 and 2020. This review provided valuable insights into the evolution of wind energy projects in the country. Additionally, desktop research and stakeholder interviews were conducted, including a review of policy reports, official documents, and relevant publications from governmental and non-governmental sources. This multi-sourced data approach strengthened and validated the findings obtained from interviews.

In exploring the development of the offshore wind energy sector in Bulgaria, a media analysis method was employed to gather insights and discourses related to this completely new technology to an audience largely unfamiliar with its specifics and the emerging industry. The approach involved meticulous data collection from over 25 media publications spanning from 2021 onwards, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives and nuances were captured.

The process began with the identification of reputable media outlets covering energy-related topics within Bulgaria. These sources were carefully selected to encompass a variety of formats, including newspapers, online news portals, and industry-specific publications. By casting a wide net, the analysis aimed to capture a comprehensive snapshot of the discourse surrounding offshore wind energy within the country.

Each publication was scrutinized to extract pertinent information regarding the status, challenges, and prospects of offshore wind energy development in Bulgaria. This involved extracting key data points such as investment trends, regulatory frameworks, technological advancements, and stakeholder perspectives. Additionally, attention was paid to the tone and framing of the coverage, including any biases or underlying narratives present in the reporting.

Although participant observation and focus groups were not feasible due to logistical constraints, a triangulation approach was employed to cross-validate the data. Integrating insights from multiple sources allowed for a robust examination of wind energy project development in the region, enhancing the overall validity and reliability of the study's conclusions. The comprehensive data collection and analysis process facilitated a thorough understanding of the challenges, opportunities, and implications surrounding wind energy initiatives in the North-East region.

3.2 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

Before the introduction of legislation governing offshore wind energy deployment in Bulgaria, media publications largely depicted the industry's economic potential as a promising avenue for future growth. Commentary frequently underscored the anticipated economic benefits, framing offshore wind energy as a potential arena for competition between Bulgaria and Romania, given their similar developmental stages.

However, following the introduction and subsequent voting of the law in Parliament, the narrative underwent a significant shift. Media coverage pivoted towards highlighting clashes of opinions and conflicts surrounding the legislation, with opposition stemming from a mix of genuine concerns and politically motivated agendas. Articles began emphasizing resistance to offshore wind energy projects, even though the proposed zoning outlined in the draft law had not yet been implemented. This resistance was particularly fueled by apprehensions regarding tourism, fisheries, and potential environmental impacts.

Despite extensive discourse on potential environmental risks, there was a noticeable dearth of emphasis on the economic benefits for local communities. While analyses of best practices and environmental risk governance from other countries were accessible, they received limited exploration in media coverage.

A notable imbalance in media representation emerged between perspectives from economic experts and those from environmental organizations and industrial associations. Typically, a handful of economic experts were juxtaposed against numerous associations and environmental organizations, often lacking substantive data or evidence to bolster their arguments.

The debate largely sidestepped discussions on potential institutional frameworks or relationship organizations aimed at regulating and effectively governing offshore wind energy projects. Instead, there was a prevailing sentiment against prioritizing the legislation, with calls for Bulgaria to cease development in both offshore and onshore sectors. Frequently, discussions veered towards advocating for nuclear energy as a superior alternative, citing its baseload power capabilities and low-carbon footprint, although the significantly higher cost of new nuclear power generation assets per unit of electricity generated remained unaddressed. It is suspected that opposition to offshore wind energy in the Black Sea may have been further inflamed by lobbying efforts from the nuclear sector.

Acknowledging the inherent bias in media coverage, our analysis recognizes the prevalence of perspectives from project opponents compared to those from project developers. While this doesn't necessarily imply that opponents possess more detailed arguments, it underscores their vocal presence in the discourse.

One limitation of our analysis is the absence of direct interviews or contact with offshore wind energy project developers, primarily due to the reluctance of potential investors to disclose their plans amid the uncertain regulatory environment. However, we endeavored to offset this limitation by thoroughly analyzing available sources, which offered nuanced insights into various arguments and viewpoints.

In conclusion, the media portrayal of offshore wind energy deployment in Bulgaria reflects a complex interplay of economic aspirations, environmental concerns, and political dynamics. Going forward, fostering balanced discussions that consider both the potential benefits and risks associated with offshore wind energy projects, while incorporating diverse perspectives from all stakeholders, is crucial.

4 WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN NORTH EAST REGION

To better understand the context and development of wind energy in the North-East region, a comprehensive list of phases and critical instances of change was compiled. It includes main phases/time periods in the development of wind energy in Bulgaria, indicating critical instances of change that precede the transition from one phase to another. These instances could be in many political and socio-economic forms, from new policies or regulations, new investors popping up, a change in incumbent parties, protests, a new form of participations, to a change in power relations or cultural beliefs. These developments may occur at different vertical and horizontal structural levels, but are characterized by sector-wide impact.

Historically, the wind industry in Bulgaria (and the development of the RES sector in general) has gone through six stages. The phases are conventionally divided on the basis of key events and impulses that qualitatively changed the institutional frameworks and governance arrangement. Generally, they are the following:

Table 2. Phases of wind energy development in Bulgaria

Initial phase: establishing the industry			Phase of self-sustaining growth		
Research & development (the very first steps)	First commercial projects	"Boom" in sector development	"Freezing" (decline) of sector development	Revival based on market logic	A look beyond the regional and the traditional aspect

Formation of research and technological competences	Setting up a strategic framework and policies	Sharp increase in installed wind capacity	Retroactive measures	Regulatory stimulation of the production of green energy for further liberalization of the electricity market	Adoption of the EU strategy on offshore renewable energy, recognizing the Black Sea potential for blue energy
Resource mobilization and needs assessment	Presentation of funding schemes	Formation of expectations for technological progress	Institutional barriers	The Energy Strategy was adopted in 2020	The war in Ukraine opened the debate about accelerated deployment of renewables, including offshore wind energy in Bulgaria
Pilot projects, creation of informal networks of economic agents	Entering of foreign investors	Irrational behavior of stakeholders	The delayed effects of the global financial crisis was being felt	The Integrated Plan on Energy and Climate for 2021-2030 was adopted	
	First Law in 2007, which was based on European framework - the first Renewable and Alternative Energy and Biofuels Act	New financial schemes attracted national and foreign investors	Negative opinion and attitudes	Opening of sector to new investments	Proposal of a Law on Renewable Energy Sources in Maritime Spaces
		The regulatory frameworks was not able to control and balance the opportunistic expectations	Case C-141/14 of the Court of EU against Bulgaria due to failure fulfill obligations in relation to natural habitats, wild species and birds conservation	Projects with the aim of own consumption	Recovery and Resilience Plan for Bulgaria, which foresees country to survey suitable areas for the construction of onshore and offshore wind farms ("go-to-areas" as two different milestones in the plan)
		Formation of negative opinion and attitudes	Declined Investors' interest	Entirely market-driven logic	Regional Just transition plans – pending issue
				Entry of self-consumption business models that attracts small investors	Cross-border initiatives - Bulgaria and Romania started discussions over cross-border renewable energy projects in the Black Sea
				Technology prices dropped noticeably, which feeds healthy competitiveness	
				The EU's more ambitious climate targets were introduced (toward low carbon technologies)	
				Public became more accepting	First pilot project testing floating offshore wind concept in the Black Sea approved by Horizon Europe

					<p>New pilots and participatory practices were set to be tested, e.g. energy assistance program developed by "Dobrotich Wind" JSC with benefits worth EUR 7.5 million for the population of 2 villages located close to 2 wind farms of the company</p> <p>Legislation on energy communities in Bulgaria - an unresolved issue going forward</p> <p>Introduction of Offshore Wind Energy Act</p> <p>Increased role of twin transition (digital and green transition)</p> <p>Accelerated deployment of deep tech in the sector (novel technologies entering the market)</p>
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Up to 2007	2007-2010	2010-2012	01.07.2012-2018	2018-2021	2022-
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Figure 5 . Timeline of wind energy development within the regional x between the years of 2008-2023.

4.1 PRE-PERIOD

Although Bulgarian state research on the potential of wind energy dates back to the early 1980s, it was commercialized after the first years of the new century. The first industrial wind generator in Bulgaria was put into operation near the town of Aheloy (Burgas province) for the needs of an eco-farm in 1998. Generally, the phase of R&D and small demonstration projects took place between the 1980s until the beginning of 2006. In 2007 Bulgaria became a full member of the EU and the European regulations that came into force in this period and in the preceding years following the accession period, determined the raised investors interest.

Key events before the country's accession to the EU are: 1) the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in 2002, and 2) the adoption of the Energy Act (EA) in 2003 oriented to the development of the renewable energy sector. Although the Act established general conditions for efficient use and generation of energy from renewable sources it did not contain concrete investment incentives. This is a weakness of the document, since specific investor incentives and initiatives, especially in an underdeveloped market segment, are to provide direction and stimulate project proposals.

Renewable energy sources can be considered both as a whole and in isolation. In Bulgaria, solar and wind energy are developing at an accelerated pace following similar phases of development in the past 20 years. Growth in wind power capacity has been relatively flatter, but again over 700 MW has been built in 10-15 years. According to the Trade Register currently there are about 155 active companies operating wind farms in Bulgaria.

In 2007 Bulgaria joined the European Union and, as part of the accession process, accepted mandatory obligations for the development of renewable energy production. In 2007 Bulgaria adopted the **Renewable and Alternative Energy Sources and Biofuels Act** with the purpose to establish a system for producing electricity from renewable energy sources (RES) and to create a favorable investment climate. Under it, electricity from RES was supported primarily through a feed-in tariff (FiT) scheme.

Eligible producers of electricity from RES were entitled to enter into long-term power purchase agreements (PPAs) with the Public Supplier, the State-owned National Electricity Company, EAD or directly with end-suppliers. The suppliers were required by law to purchase all RES-generated electricity, other than that sold on the free market and that which was used for the plants' own consumption.

The FiTs were subject to annual review by the Bulgarian Energy and Water Regulatory Commission (EWRC or the Regulator). The law provided a formula by which the Regulator calculated the applicable FiT rate, creating a certain amount of transparency in the system, where FiTs could not decrease by more than 5% per year.

Thus, as of 2008, RES investors in Bulgaria were guaranteed long-term PPAs for the purchase of all the electricity they produced at preferential prices that would not decrease by more than 5% per year.

In 2009, according to the Directive 2009/28/EC, the above-mentioned Bulgaria's target was to achieve 16% of its total energy consumption from RES by 2020. The FiT program already introduced, however, did not attract enough investment in the renewable energy sector for Bulgaria to meet its new EU obligations.

In 2011 Bulgaria adopted the **Energy from Renewable Sources Act (ERSA)** in order to create a more favorable investment climate and to achieve the new EU targets. **It promoted a more attractive and stable FiT support program for renewable energy projects.**

ERSA confirmed that once a particular FiT applied to an eligible plant, that plant was entitled to the specified tariff for the full duration of its PPA (20 years for solar, geothermal and biomass, 15 years for hydro up to 1 MW and 12 years for wind). ERSA also specifically provided that suppliers were required to purchase all electricity produced from RES at the fixed FiT, other than the electricity that producers elected to sell on the free market and that used for the plants' own consumption.

Thus, the 2011 incentive program resulted in substantial investment and enabled Bulgaria to be ahead of schedule to meet its EU targets by 2013. Furthermore, it was ranked second among the top ten emerging markets for renewable energy. While in 2004, the share of renewable energy in the country's final consumption was 9.1% due to the participation/contribution of hydropower plants in the energy mix built in the past, more than ten years later, the target was exceeded seven years ahead of the official deadline in 2020.

The period between 2010-2012 is when the first large commercial wind farms were established and the phase of experiments and demonstration projects has already ended. It is important to note that the first commercial projects were built with knowledge and based on the experience of foreign partners or entrepreneurs. By 2012, larger investors gradually entered the market, bringing with them professional knowledge on the development and management of renewable energy projects.

In fact, after the initial investment boom of installed wind turbines between 2010-2012, the Bulgarian energy system and society find themselves unprepared to cope with the difficulties arising from system cost increase due to the support granted to the first RES projects in the form of feed-in-tariffs. In addition, the undeveloped regulatory framework and lack of administrative capacity to manage renewable energy projects have slowed development and undermined public confidence in such projects. It was 2012 when Bulgaria realized that it would reach its target ahead of schedule and that the incentives programme would continue to attract more investment in the renewables sector, and

decided to take measures to withhold further investment, especially in solar and wind. As a result, the upward trajectory of installed capacity was interrupted by significantly deteriorated market conditions, a succession of stop-and-go policies and retroactive government interventions, leading to a loss of investors' interest and an unstable economic environment.

Moreover, changes to the scheme were made almost every year between 2012-2015, negatively affecting the stability of the legal framework and the confidence of investors in the Bulgarian energy market. In 2012 the Regulator adopted a decision, which introduced a retroactive temporary grid access fee for all RES, where for some projects the fee reached 39% of their FiT. This led to the **gradual decrease of the FiTs until their final revocation for RES projects to be developed after 2013, which in practice put an end to RES investments in Bulgaria for the coming years.**

In parallel to the euphoria and the construction of wind farms, public discontent was slowly but surely growing, caused by allegations of excessive public expenditure on subsidies, lack of control and alleged mass violations in the green sector. The requests were mostly related to violations in the construction of wind and solar parks. As a result, in 2010 the government-initiated checks on the procedures for legalizing green electricity production, simultaneously introducing measures against the growth of new capacities in all types of green energy. Subsequently, it turned out that there were violations, but they were insignificant. In any case, political uncertainty, contradicting political signals and the lack of political will and adequate mechanisms for managing RES energy, led to an outflow of investors' interest for almost 10 years.

In 2014 Bulgaria introduced a fee on the revenues of PV and wind farms at the rate of 20% of their FiT (without VAT). This fee was pronounced unconstitutional by the Constitutional Court in 2014. However, the producers were still unable to recover part of the fees paid after it was declared unconstitutional. The end of July 2019 was the deadline for claiming reimbursement of the 20% fee withheld for the period July-August 2014.

Bulgaria also reduced the amount of energy that could be purchased at preferential FiT prices to the quantity of electricity produced on average by the same category of plants minus the producer's own electricity consumption (e.g. 1,188 MWh per annum for most PV plants). Thus, electricity produced in excess of that threshold could only be sold on the free market. Also, the operation of a balancing market has been introduced, and RES producers were required to become part of a balancing group and pay monthly settlements to the coordinator of their balancing group.

In 2015 the authorities further reduced the investors' FiT payment rights by requiring RES producers to pay a monthly fee to the Electricity System Security Fund (ESSF) amounting to 5% of their revenue, with VAT excluded. The above measures led to numerous court proceedings from RES producers against the competent authorities in the country, the majority of which ended with a positive outcome for the producers. Certain big investors started international arbitration proceedings against Bulgaria.

Since 2015, the situation with existing RES has gradually become more stable and, as a result, there has been an increase in M&A activity in the market.

Table 3. Key events between 1980 and 2018 ey events

Key events between 1980 and 2018 (before the study focus period)
1980 - the first wind generator has been installed

1997 - a prototype of a generator combining the wind with a photovoltaic system is put in exploitation in 1997 by the Technical university, Varna, North-East region

1998 - the first industrial wind generator had entered into exploitation near the town Aheloi for the purposes of an eco-farm

2008 - the fourth wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Kaliakra”, entered into exploitation (Kavarna, Dobrich region), North-East region

2009 - the biggest wind energy park in Bulgaria – “St. Nikola” has been built (Kavarna, Dobrich region), North-East region

2010 - the third wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Vetrokom”, entered into exploitation (Kazanlak, Stara Zagora region)

2010 - the Bulgarian wind energy association has been established

2010 - the seventh wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity (together with the following park) – “Haos”, entered into exploitation (Kavarna, Dobrich region), North-East region

2012 - the seventh wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Kavarna”, entered into exploitation (Kavarna, Dobrich region), North-East region

2012 - the second wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Suvorovo”, entered into exploitation (Suvorovo, Varna region), North-East region

2012 - the fifth wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Contact consul”, entered into exploitation (Kazanlak, Stara Zagora region)

2012 - the sixth wind energy park in Bulgaria according to the capacity – “Vranino”, entered into exploitation (Kavarna, Dobrich region), North-East region

4.2 PHASE 1: REVIVAL BASED ON MARKET LOGIC (2018-2021)

After several years of stagnation in the sector, marked by changes in regulations and a lack of confidence in the system, market mechanisms gradually began to recover. The reasons for the decline are described in more detail in the previous chapter (see 4.1. Pre-period). In general, this is a period in which investors start exploring the opportunities in the Bulgarian market again. Meantime the prices of new technologies are falling and entering the market, which gives rise to healthy competition.

It is difficult to point out one single and leading practice (critical instance of change) that is responsible for the revival in the sector. Rather, it is due to a series of small steps and decisions based on the

natural development of market relations, knowledge exchange and technology transfer after several years of stagnation. However, there are some political-economic dimensions that should be paid particular attention to:

Starting from 2016 to 2018 the Bulgarian government adopted certain changes to encourage small roof-top power plants and power plants with installed capacity up to 4 MW by limiting the FiT application only to these small producers.

Moreover, in 2018 the state changed the legislation in order to arrange for producers with total installed capacity of 4 MW and above 4 MW to enter into feed-in premium agreements and terminate the long-term PPAs. Such premiums were arranged to be paid by the Electricity System Security Fund (ESSF). This could be considered among main reasons that had led to divergence in the sector and emergence of moderate optimism among investors and stakeholders.

Since mid-2018, every producer that received any premium under the feed-in premium agreements paid the ESSF a monthly fee of 5% of income resulting from the sale of electricity from RES.

In 2019 any deals with producers with a total installed capacity of 1 MW and above were conducted via the organized fund market at a freely negotiated price. However, such an option was not available to power plants that come into operation after 1 January 2019.

Moreover, at the end of 2020 and the beginning of 2021, key legislative changes were adopted, which could be seen as **a critical instances of change** that laid the foundation for the next stage in the development of RES energy in the country – a second wave characterized by increased investors' interest and a first look beyond the regional and the traditional aspect. As of 1 January 2021 regulatory stimulation of the production of green energy for further liberalization of the electricity market was put in place: **new renewable power plants entering into operation were not obliged to pay 5% of their revenues to the Electricity System Security Fund**; in addition a proposal to remove all electricity producers with an installed capacity of more than 500 KW from the power exchange was also adopted (up to that moment it was mandatory for power plants above 1 MW). The changes were included in a package of amendments to the Energy Act. It is believed that they are key steps towards the continuation of the energy reform for full liberalization of the electricity market and integration of the national market into the common European energy market.

In 2020 the National representative study in the domain of public attitudes towards renewable energy was published by Sofia University.²

In general, the analysis of survey data on public perceptions toward renewable energy sources (RES) in Bulgaria shows a positive attitude toward green energy technologies, despite low levels of awareness and a lack of meaningful citizen inclusion in the energy transition process. As of the beginning of 2021, the social acceptability of low-carbon technologies and the benefits Bulgarian citizens associate with them stem mainly from public concerns about environmental and climate change issues. The contribution of RES to avoiding environmental problems, including the fight against climate challenges, has the greatest weight in citizens' decisions regarding financial support provision for RES expansion policies. However, another important determinant for this decision is the perception of the energy transition as an inclusive and transparent process. The capability of

² Trifonova, M., Социална приемливост на енергийните технологии в България [Social acceptance of energy technologies in Bulgaria], Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, 2020.

administrative authorities and institutional bodies to gain citizens' trust also influences social acceptance.

Notably, in regions with more wind installations, such as the North-East region, a higher level of awareness is observed, correlating with a higher level of social acceptance. In North Eastern Bulgaria, where most onshore wind power plants would be located, citizens have shown higher levels of awareness and readiness to support renewable energy technology deployment compared to other regions of the country. Results of the YouGov survey, conducted by the European Climate Foundation, also support similar conclusions, as 70 percent of Bulgarian survey participants, expressed willingness to live near an offshore wind farm against 18 percent who would oppose it.³

Figure 5. Installed capacity of onshore wind energy and level of awareness regarding the technology

The respondents associate renewables and the technologies for their utilization primarily with the environmental benefits of zero-emission energy generation. When it comes to the perceived economic benefits of green technologies, respondents are more skeptical. Only 56% believe that higher RES shares would increase employment, and 58% of the respondents consider it as a driver for

³ European Climate Foundation, Cross-EU polling on renewable energy, Conducted by YouGov, October 2021.

economic growth. As Figure 2 illustrates, between 5% and 10% disagree with the listed benefits that could result from more intensive RES use.⁴

In 2020 a draft of an Energy Strategy was published with the following five priorities: 1) to guarantee the security of energy supply; 2) to attain the targets for renewable energy; 3) to increase the energy efficiency; 4) to develop a competitive energy market and policy for the purpose of meeting the energy needs; 5) to protect the interests of the consumers. However, until now Bulgaria is lacking an adopted Energy Strategy and a new draft of the document is currently under public discussion.

Also, the Integrated Plan on Energy and Climate for 2021-2030 was set to provide for the development of the RES sector to 27% of the gross end consumption and therefore the Bulgarian Government expected that PV installed capacity in Bulgaria would triple by 2030. With the adoption of the European Climate Change Act, the European Union has reaffirmed its intentions to stick to its ambition to achieve a carbon neutral economy by 2050. However, the measures set out in the strategy document were not sufficiently aligned with the EU's vision for decarbonisation and a green energy transition up to that moment (according to a CSD study).

Currently, only small-scale producers with installed capacity up to 30 kW can be subject to FiT. After regulatory changes from October 2019, around 370 power plants were enabled to sell electricity on the free market. By the middle of 2021 most of the RES producers with installed capacity of 0.5-1 MW signed feed-in premium agreements. FIT is applied mainly to new rooftop solar panels or facade photovoltaic installations with low capacity. Preferential prices are set and regulated by the Energy and Water Regulatory Commission (EWRC). RES producers are not given priority access to the grid, so connecting their systems is subject to the general provisions of the energy legislation.

As a result of the above-mentioned changes applications for new renewable energy plants are growing every year, and this shows the need for urgent measures to ease the procedures for the construction of solar and wind plants, as well as for grid development.

In this phase, and more specifically towards the end of 2020, the question of how the government will promote investments in renewable energy and the creation of shared energy communities becomes particularly prominent - themes that will unfold in the coming years and will be reflected in key national documents such as the territorial plans for a just transition created in 2022 in the regions of the country most affected by the transition.

The Territorial Just Transition Plans (2030 horizon) are an important strategic document that will allow the unlocking of the European Just Transition Fund (JTF). These plans address the NUTS3 territories (regions) that are most affected by the coal transition in the few coming years and the population/workers there in order to promote a balanced socio-economic transition by providing targeted financial support. By the end of 2022, at the European level, all territorial plans had been adopted by the Commission, except Bulgaria's. In 2023, this issue is still unresolved and the country faces the threat of losing the opportunity to benefit from funds amounting to around EUR 1.2 billion.

Another issue is that social tensions and insecurity among the population generate systemic stress and distrust in the results of the transition.

⁴ Trifonova, M. (2022). Public acceptance and willingness to pay for renewable energy in Bulgaria. IFAC-PapersOnLine, 55(11), 138-143.

Offshore wind development in Bulgaria / North-East region

The regional case study places specific emphasis on offshore wind energy, acknowledging its significance in the study. The focus on offshore wind developments intensified in 2019, prompting independent researchers and the public to actively engage with the topic. The North-East, being one of the two maritime regions, plays a pivotal role not only in onshore but also in offshore wind developments.

The EU Strategy on Offshore Renewable Energy provided the initial impetus and a strategic signal for stakeholders in the region, signaling that the energy component of the local blue economy deserves increased attention. This document underscores a robust commitment to developing the European marine energy sector and advancing climate neutrality. Additionally, the strategy recognizes the Black Sea's potential in meeting EU energy and climate targets, emphasizing the importance of fostering collaboration and coordination among diverse stakeholders.

Policymakers in countries such as Poland, Estonia, Latvia, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, Greece, and Cyprus—representing emerging markets in the EU—are currently grappling with a challenging energy situation. However, they feel empowered to take swift action in response to the EU Strategy on Offshore Renewable Energy.

The EU Strategy on Offshore Renewable Energy served as a catalyst for significant studies conducted in the field by independent institutes, including the Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD), a Bulgaria-based European policy institution. Collaborating with the World Bank and the Publication Office of the EU, CSD concentrated on national-specific assumptions and data, conducting expert assessments of the potential and possible development prospects of the offshore wind energy industry.

CSD's publications and information initiatives have elevated the topic on the political agenda, particularly in the context of achieving energy transition and ensuring the energy independence of the country. Those assessments are in-depth, expert-based and complemented by surveys and interviews with dozens of stakeholders not only to verify the outcomes but to assure that no one is left behind.

Some of these analyses could be seen as sectors' pre-assessment and are a necessary step to serve policymakers and authorities in setting short-and long-term priorities in a national context.

In 2021 the CSD published an assessment of the Black sea offshore potential under the title “Wind Power Generation in Bulgaria”.⁵ The results testify to the country's offshore wind energy potential as it could become a leading energy source for transition and achieving climate change targets. To stress this a technical and economic assessment of the Bulgarian Exclusive Economic Zone in the Black Sea identifying favorable deployment areas for offshore wind power generation has been provided.

The study's findings revealed the technical offshore wind energy potential in the Bulgarian section of the Black Sea to be approximately 116 GW. Of this total capacity, around 26 GW (one-fifth) could be achieved using mature bottom-fixed technology, while the remaining capacity would necessitate floating power plants. The area with the best wind resource and the largest deployment potential is situated in the northernmost part of the Bulgarian EEZ, along the border with Romanian territorial waters. Covering an effective area of 405 km², with wind speeds ranging between 7.6 and 8 m/s at a height of 150 m, this specific section of the Black Sea has a maximum depth of 60 m, making the installation of fixed platforms viable due to reduced technological costs.

⁵ Center for the Study of Democracy, Wind Power Generation in Bulgaria, September 2021.

A significant contribution of the report is that it recognised the role of all other environmental, economic and community groups with an interest in coastal areas. It also focuses attention on the need for supporting infrastructure and regional cooperation to achieve efficiencies, economies of scale and knowledge sharing. In the development of offshore energy, Bulgaria could benefit from job creation, new technological clusters, and local equipment supply chains. Moreover, the offshore wind industry could transform the two largest Bulgarian ports (Varna and Burgas) into decarbonization hubs, which will contribute to further development of the sector in the Black Sea.

Another significant development entails a landscape-level transformation and external pressure on the Bulgarian government to establish concrete, non-binding targets for offshore wind deployment. As outlined in the TEN-E Regulation, the Black Sea Basin is recognized as a priority offshore grid corridor at the EU level for the development of offshore grids. Leveraging the substantial wind potential in the region, an energy island project has been proposed to bring benefits to both EU countries (Romania and Bulgaria) and non-EU countries (Turkey, Georgia, Ukraine), contributing to the broader EU internal market. In response to this, an internal working group has been established at the Ministry of Energy.

4.3 PHASE 2: A LOOK BEYOND TRADITIONAL AND REGIONAL (2022-2024)

The period after 2022 is dynamic and demonstrates transformation as reaction of crises, namely the war of Russia in Ukraine. In the background of Natural market dynamics and technological development in the wind sector (novel technologies appeared) along with opportunities for international cooperation continued to face political uncertainty. All this in light of the country's ambitious long-term renewable energy targets. External and difficult-to-control events such as the coronavirus pandemic and the military conflict in Ukraine have in turn become catalysts for change by bringing to the fore issues in respect of the need for energy independence and system resilience. All this along with the urgent and still unresolved topics of energy citizenship and energy communities. In a short time, the resolution of a number of deferred issues of a strategic and operational nature related to the governance of wind energy became a national priority.

Attracting national and foreign capital has turned into a necessity, and the established European funds and mechanisms into an opportunity, which at this moment the country is missing.

All this along with urgent, but still unresolved topics of energy citizenship and development of participatory practices, e.g. different forms of energy cooperatives. In a short time, the resolution of a number of deferred issues of a strategic and operational nature related to the management of wind energy is emerging.

By 2023, investors in the country are active and in a positive and with positive expectations towards the development of the sector. A part of the projects frozen years ago are in the process of searching for opportunities to update project proposals and reinforce implementation. Most of the investors are aware of the need for cooperation with other stakeholders and are looking for dialogue in early exploratory phases of their projects to avoid conflicts in the future. These are conversations with eco organizations, farmers, researchers, animal advocates, etc. In addition, the regulatory framework and slow procedures put investors and regional authorities (municipalities) in constant communication in search of symbiosis and speeding up the processes for zoning and building permits.

Below are present two good examples of investors who plan to build wind farms in the coming years in the North-East region. Representatives of both investors were interviewed in the course of the study, so the processes and difficulties they face will be further presented and analyzed.

Dobrotich Wind Park (Investor: CWP)

Dobrotich Wind Park stands as a significant renewable energy initiative in the North-East Region, designed to supply electricity to approximately 440,000 homes and reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 1,350,000 tonnes annually. The project, situated about 60 km west of Varna in the municipalities of Vetrino and Valchi dol, is in the process of installing 74 wind turbines and associated infrastructure. Aligned with the government's commitment to the European Commission's target of achieving 27% renewable energy in Bulgaria's energy mix by 2030, Dobrotich Wind Park aims to contribute to this goal.

Intended to bring economic benefits to local communities and the Varna region, the project has encountered a setback. The investor has temporarily halted project implementation due to tensions with locally influential corporate entities who own a historical site and an entertainment park within a large area of the municipality. A public dispute has ensued, with the owners of these establishments asserting that the wind turbines will negatively impact tourism, a sector they actively develop. Consequently, this dispute has influenced public attitudes towards the project, creating uncertainties about its future progress.

Wind park near Balchik (Investor: wpd)

The company holds the rights for constructing two wind power plants with a combined capacity of 75 MW, concurrently exploring opportunities and suitable sites for additional projects. Market estimates suggest an investment in such capacity would range between 90 to 120 million euros.

Their ongoing projects near the villages of Sokolovo and Trigortsi are in an advanced stage of development. Over the years, they have obtained building permits and developed comprehensive technical documentation. Currently, the company is planning to deploy more efficient turbines with a modern design, aligning with market dynamics.

Actively engaged in social responsibility, the company regularly conducts meetings with local authorities and interested community groups. They assert that the local municipality is highly supportive, maintaining positive relationships with local landowners and agricultural businesses.

Advancing Offshore Wind Energy in Bulgaria

The Russian invasion of Ukraine has spurred Bulgarian policymakers to prioritize energy independence from Russia, leading to an exploration of alternative options for large-scale decarbonization in the power and industrial sectors. Bulgarian Members of Parliament (MPs) across political parties expressed support for a new legislative framework during a parliamentary hearing in March 2022 to facilitate the deployment of offshore wind energy projects. Despite passing the first reading in the energy committee in September 2022, the proposed framework faced obstacles in Parliament due to political instability, leading to snap elections and the dissolution of Parliament. A revised version of the law has been presented for a new vote in December 2023.

While national policymakers recognize the future role of marine renewable energy in Bulgaria, the current National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) still sets a relatively modest target for renewable energy, aiming for only 27 percent of gross final energy consumption by 2030. The NECP primarily focuses on a slight increase in onshore wind capacity, with no consideration for offshore wind

additions. Integrating large-scale offshore wind energy into Bulgaria's territorial waters could significantly contribute to achieving NECP objectives by promoting low-carbon economic development, fostering the adoption of competitive and secure energy sources, and reducing dependence on fossil fuel imports. The revised NECP should align with higher renewables and energy efficiency targets proposed by the European Commission and the REPowerEU objectives. The updated document is anticipated in the spring of 2024 and currently running public discussions demonstrate that it will follow the RES targets discussed in the Energy Transition Commission, meaning that offshore renewable energy targets will be put in to the simulations of the Plan for the first time. In general, the absence of strategic documents such as the revised NECP or the National Energy Strategy (which is still in draft form) fails to provide clear signals to attract investors and ensure predictability. These documents lack ambitious wind energy targets and neglect important issues such as skills and workforce preparation, as well as the implementation of the SET Plan.

The Energy Transition Commission, a sub-commission to the Consultative Council for the European Green Deal at the Council of Ministers, has projected offshore wind development prospects of 0.5 GW by 2030 and 3.3 GW by 2050. Consequently, the Climate Neutrality Roadmap voted by the Parliament estimates offshore wind deployment targets of 500 MW to 1,000 MW by 2030 in an accelerated scenario and 2,500 MW by 2040.

The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) also plays a role in Bulgaria's long-term decarbonization efforts, proposing measures such as simplification of licensing and permitting procedures for renewables investments, streamlined grid connection timelines, and dedicated areas for onshore wind. However, political instability has significantly delayed the implementation of the NRRP. It is expected that in early 2024 Bulgaria will publish a spatial plan for accelerated wind power development, including areas for offshore wind energy deployment, in line with the engagement in the NRRP framework.

An important development that will serve as a test of the reactions of the coastal population in the North-East of Bulgaria towards offshore wind turbines will be the implementation of a Horizon-funded demonstration project at the natural gas exploration platform in the Black Sea Galata, operated by Petroceltic. According to the project outline, within the next two years, a single 5-MW floating wind turbine will be installed in the section of the Bulgarian EEZ, marking the first wind turbine in the Black Sea. This project will provide valuable insights into public acceptance and the technical feasibility of offshore wind energy in the region.

The establishment of the Black Sea Renewable Energy Coalition launched in the summer of 2023, is another pivotal step in accelerating the offshore wind sector's development in the region. The coalition brings together stakeholders from Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, and Turkey to exchange knowledge, share best practices, and build a common understanding of challenges. This network-building effort can collectively address technical, environmental, and social barriers and benefit capacity building in the regional markets for offshore low-carbon energy and coal dependent energy systems' decarbonization.

In the meantime, in September 2023 the first edition of the Marine Renewable Energy Academy, an international summer school organized by Sofia University, took place in Burgas. This was the first educational initiative aiming at disseminating knowledge about techno-economic aspects of marine renewable energy and facilitating knowledge exchange with leading educational institutions from Denmark, UK and USA.

The North Eastern region of Bulgaria has significant potential for the development of local supply chains, which could create new green job opportunities for small businesses. Additionally, the Bulgarian Maritime University, located in Varna, produces well-trained maritime specialists who can be employed in the construction and maintenance of onshore wind farms. VESTAS, the largest European manufacturer, installer, and service provider for the wind turbine industry, has a subsidiary operating in the region, which provides a skilled workforce for the maintenance of wind farms in Bulgaria and Romania. As a result, the project is expected to generate local employment opportunities in all phases of the project lifecycle, particularly in the construction and installation of the wind park (over 1 000 local employees per GW installed capacity), operations and maintenance (approximately 250 workers per GW), and project development and management (approximately 200 workers per GW).

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of wind and offshore wind development in North-East region of Bulgaria, the analysis reveals a nuanced landscape when examined through the lens of the three pillars of energy justice: distributional justice, procedural justice, and recognition justice.

Wind and offshore wind development in Bulgaria showcase a potential to contribute significantly to distributional justice. Projects such as the Dobrotich Wind Park aim to provide electricity to a considerable number of homes, offering tangible benefits to a broad segment of the population. However, challenges arise when local tensions and disputes between economic sectors emerge, such as the case where the Dobrotich Wind Park project was temporarily frozen due to concerns from politically linked corporate structures about potential impacts on tourism.

The procedural aspects of wind energy projects in Bulgaria reveal a mixed picture. While companies engage in advanced planning, secure building permits, and maintain ongoing discussions with local authorities and communities, instances of project delays due to political tensions underscore challenges in ensuring a fair and transparent decision-making process. Striking a balance between efficient project deployment and inclusive, transparent procedures is essential to uphold procedural justice.

Recognition justice in the context of wind development in Bulgaria revolves around acknowledging and respecting the concerns, perspectives, and rights of local communities. However, it becomes obvious that a few forms of participation of the citizens have been recognized. Most of the developments and critical instances of change occur on national level with little impact from the regional governance or communities.

In summary, while wind and offshore wind development in Bulgaria present opportunities for advancing energy justice, challenges related to local tensions, political influences, and competing interests highlight the importance of carefully navigating the three pillars of energy justice to achieve a more equitable and sustainable energy transition. Balancing economic development with environmental and cultural considerations and fostering transparent and inclusive processes will be critical to addressing the complexities inherent in Bulgaria's wind energy landscape.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A critical undertaking for the blue economy growth in the North-East region is the formulation and enactment of legislation that supports the offshore wind sector in Bulgaria. Regional policymakers need to advocate for a specialized regulatory framework that aligns with the unique characteristics of the region to tailor policies to address local concerns and ensure efficient project approvals. The Offshore Wind Energy legislation should be grounded in transparent, competition-friendly principles, delineating clear allocations of risks, costs, and responsibilities among stakeholders. The establishment of consistent policies will create a stable investment environment, attracting private investments and simplifying permitting processes. By mitigating political and regulatory risks, regional governments can minimize the overall deployment cost. Drawing inspiration from mature offshore wind markets like the United Kingdom, Germany, and Denmark, the North-East region can construct robust frameworks conducive to long-term growth and sustainable blue/green development.

The formation of communities of practice, akin to the Black Sea Renewable Energy Coalition initiated in the summer of 2023, emerges as another crucial step in accelerating the development of the offshore wind sector. This coalition, encompassing stakeholders from Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, and Turkey, serves as a platform to exchange knowledge, share best practices, and foster a collective understanding of challenges. Through this collaborative effort, technical, environmental, and social barriers can be collectively addressed, contributing to capacity building in the regional markets for offshore low-carbon energy and the decarbonization of coal-dependent energy systems. Local companies and organizations from the North-East region should take an active role in the working groups of the Coalition and contribute to its agenda.

The exploration of opportunities for cross-border projects is imperative for maximizing the region's offshore wind energy potential, since the region is neighbouring Romania.. Collaborative initiatives between neighboring countries can efficiently utilize resources, optimize grid integration, and enhance energy security. By establishing interconnection mechanisms and developing joint offshore wind projects, countries can leverage strengths, attract larger investments, and achieve economies of scale.

The transformation of ports, including the two major industrial ports in Varna, into decarbonization hubs stands out as a crucial aspect of offshore wind industry development in the North-East region. Upgrading port infrastructure to support the construction, operation, and maintenance of offshore wind farms will generate job opportunities and stimulate local economies. Ports can also function as centers for manufacturing, assembly, and supply chain activities, further fostering growth in the renewable energy sector and employment.

Information campaigns play a pivotal role in raising public awareness and garnering support for offshore wind energy in the North-East region. Engaging with local communities, addressing concerns, and highlighting the environmental and economic benefits can contribute to building social acceptance. Promoting transparency, providing accurate information, and involving stakeholders in decision-making processes are essential for ensuring a smooth and inclusive energy transition.

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8 ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

All interviews have duration between 1.15 and 2 hours.

Interview with Martin Iliev	WPD, wind energy project development company	Expert with a close look at the wind energy sectoral development since 2010
Interview with Sevda Yoncheva	CWP, one of the companies developing RES project worldwide and owner of the Dobrotich Wind Park	Aim of the interview was to obtain information about the historical development of the sector and the critical instances of change. Furthermore, we spoke about the local conflicts in the implementation of the Dobrotich onshore wind project
Intreview with Nikolay Valchev	Institute of Oceanology, Bulgarian Academy of Science	Focus of the interview was the potential conflict between biodiversity and offshore wind energy in the Black Sea
Interview with Prof. Pavel Zehtindziev	Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Science	We explored Prof. Zehtindziev 's extensive experience in the impact assessment of wind energy projects on birds and spieces in the North-East region, the legal case against Bulgaria and sources of misconceptions and myths in the Bulgarian society.
Interview with Miglena Stoilova	Bulgarian Wind Energy Association	Historal development, prospects for offshore energy development and expectations for onshore wind energy growth in the North-East region

9 ANNEX 3: MEETINGS AND EVENTS ATTENDED

Date and Place	Organizer	Event Information
08.02.2023, Bucharest	Energy Policy Group	Workshop on regulatory set-up and environmental co-existence for the Black Sea countries
17.01.2024, Sofia	WWF	Presentation of WWF's recent Basic analysis of the potential for installing RES in disturbed and urbanized areas. Link
05.12.2023, COP28 Dubai, Bulgarian Pavillion	CSD in partnership with the Bulgarian Ministry of Environmental and Water	Paths to Faster Decarbonisation: Offshore Wind Energy Potential in the Three Seas Region Link
24.11.2023, Sofia	CSD	Navigating the Legal Currents of the Emerging Offshore Wind Markets Link
26.09.2023, Sofia	CSD	Unlocking the potential for onshore wind Link
13.06.2023, Sofia	CSD	Towards a Black Sea Renewable Energy Coalition: Strategic Partnership for Energy and Climate Security Link

13.06.2023, Sofia	ARC Fund	Wind Lab1: Just and Inclusive Approaches for Allocation of wind energy accelerated areas
01.03.2023, Sofia	CSD	Strengthening Policy and Governance Capacity for Blue Energy in Central and Eastern Europe Link